

Ontology-based Palaeography

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Abstract

This paper outlines the research results conducted at the DH Lab [Laboratory for the Management of Greek and Latin Digital Resources], National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) from 2020 to 2023 (and early 2024), regarding Palaeography, and Critical Editing. During this research a phrasal term was first introduced to represent a new perspective on both ontology-based knowledge and the specific vocabulary used over the last 200 years to describe handwritten text: “Ontology based Palaeography”¹, which stands for all entities comprising what we perceive as handwritten text, acknowledging the need for digital tools that permit specialists to work with a large amount of data.²

Keywords: Palaeography; Codicology; Critical editing; Textual Criticism; Stemmatics; Formal Ontologies; Basic Formal Ontology.

Classes and Individuals (Identification, Terminology, Classification)

One of the most difficult and dare I say fundamental works of a person aiming at dealing with manuscripts and manuscript studies is taxonomy, the attempt to imagine and then depict a diagram of all entities that constitute the domain we call Palaeography³ and mainly consists of the study of historic handwritten sources. At the same time the structured process to transform these historical information into a user-friendly, modern readable form, is often proved a difficult process, thus taxonomy is strongly required.

Consider for instance dictionaries and lists, chapters and sections divided in subsections, thematic aggregations of entities meticulously analyzed. From brief explanations to

¹ Guarino (2009: 1-2); Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 1-4); Duval (2015: 211).

² Both useful in Textual Criticism and Critical Editions, see Maniaci (1996: 241); Duval (2015: 100). For critical apparatus, see Maniaci (1996: 243); Duval (2015: 55); Tarrant (2016: 130-140). Accordingly, a theoretical frame providing a model in addition with digital tools is expected to prove most valuable for the *stemma* construction, see Tarrant (2016: 12-24).

³ Petrucci (1992: 17-23).

extant references and examples⁴, taxonomy is the genetic relationship – mainly in representational form (cladogram) – reflected among entities in a way that represents a shared ancestry. This hierarchical system helps Palaeographers to study and understand the Palaeographic diversity on a manuscript the way hierarchical relationships among organisms helps scientists to study and understand the biological diversity on Earth. No matter the specific domain, while attempting a taxonomy – Palaeography included – there are three major pillars to be taken into serious consideration.

– Entity identification. It comprises a recognition process while trying to understand and distinguish palaeographic features based on their distinct characteristics.

– Entity terminology. Names are often hard to assign according to a standardized system of rules: similarities, differences, positive and negative terminology are only a few of the difficulties a specialist faces while dealing with terms.

– Entity classification. Grouping palaeographic entities into a hierarchical structure, typically involving taxonomic levels as classes and subclasses, can prove hard to achieve, as palaeographic features are mostly considered multi-facet entities. The following example depicts the various granulation levels one can choose to proceed to the taxonomy of a tool, a hand, a person, a material, a substrate, a letter, or a time interval needed for a scribe to write this or that specific part of a text he just conceptualized or just copies from an *exemplar*. This modeling process may seem quite difficult for palaeographers, but I hope the following paragraphs will make it clearer.

⁴ For instance, the work of Muzerelle and its supplement by Gumbert could be considered a sophisticated and informative list, while Duval’s work resembles a dictionary. Parkes’ impressive studies on marks and signs used for pauses (e.g. punctuation), as well as his work on medieval writing skills and manuscript books, edited by Robinson and Zim, are well-documented treatises that provide a solid foundation for a taxonomy.

Image 1: Various classes provide different levels of granularity according to a specific domain. The branches illustrating these levels are provided by Basic Formal Ontology (BFO), as will be explained below.

The first and the second granularity level seem rather obvious, while from the third one and below additional knowledge and familiarization to a specific terminology is needed. For the scope of the present paper two main branches are worthy to mention here: material and immaterial entities, two subclasses of the “independent continuant” class, as illustrated in the following image. The combination of these two entities handles a large amount of information, and concepts present in handwritten textual sources.

Image 2: “Material” and “immaterial entities” as sub-classes of the mother-class “independent continuant”.

Based on the above, you and I, a book, a codex, a bifolium, and an independent leaf are all independent continuants, specifically material entities⁵. In contrast, a blank area on parchment, a prick, or a hole in a paper or papyrus leaf cannot easily be conceptualized as material entities⁶. Instead, they are immaterial entities, defined by boundaries “from” and “to”, and perceived as such due to the material entities that serve as their “bearer”. Note that for the taxonomy needed so far, no linguistic knowledge is required. Therefore, the main taxonomic branches, “material entities” and “immaterial entities” lie on a firm, materialistic foundation of palaeographic features⁷, an aspect common to both the sciences and Palaeography.

⁵ Maniaci (2002: 39); Agati (2010: 58, 64,83).

⁶ Smith, Varzi (2002: 140).

⁷ Zaccarello (2011:35).

Image 3: Monacensis Latinus 4660, f. 107r, lin. 3: *Deinde Maria Magdalena.*⁸ Strokes can clearly be perceived as material entities, that is objects⁹, while “empty areas” (e.g. spaces intentionally left blank) are considered immaterial entities that come into existence thanks to the surrounding objects (strokes and parchment).

Let us recapitulate. An ink-stroke is a material entity, a person, a parchment folium too, but not a white space, which is clearly an area between e.g. two strokes. These assertions we just made comprise relationships mainly defined by an “is-type” relationship. To conclude:

- Taxonomies are mainly “is-type” relationships, often visualized as cladograms, lists, or even treatises, yet all governed by a complexity mostly of “is-type” relationships.
- Terminology is important for entity perception. From a more materialistic, therefore palaeographic, perspective, handwritten text should be perceived not as a Latin-derived “textile” – which refers to the quality of an object or an aggregate of objects – but rather as a Greek-derived *κείμενον* (keimenon), “a thing that lies over there”.

Object properties (“has-type” inter-entity connection)

While “is-type” classification provides all necessary elements for further consideration on the nature of the paleographic entities observed in manuscripts, there are clear evidence that material entities provide information not only for themselves but for entities that ceased to exist, nevertheless existed at some time. A scribe, a tool (pen or quill), a

⁸ To be more accurate, the transcription provided might vary, as the specific passage of the Monacensis Latinus extensively uses abbreviation techniques. As lower-case (minuscule) symbols historically established a lower-case system for language graphemic representation along with the already existed upper-case system in both Greek and Latin (see Petrucci: 1992: 35,58), the transcription must be considered a transformative process that generates graphemic variants. In such a frame the above-mentioned passage might be digitally transcribed as follows: DEINDE MARIA MAGDALENA / *deinde maria magdalena* / *Deinde Maria Magdalena*, and so on. I used the term “digitally” to imply that empirical terms like “diplomatic” and semi-diplomatic” transcription comprise in fact traces of former efforts to delineate the transformation level applied while transferring objects and areas from a material entity (e.g. historical manuscript) to another material entity (e.g. the researchers’ paper notepad). This process involves a certain degree of transformation: brevigraph expansion, punctuation update, additional symbols for row end and side (page, or recto/verso) beginnings. For a firm, well-defined paleographic classification, diplomatic and semi diplomatic transcriptions fall into the classification of “processes”, one of the two major pillars of a BFO [Basic Formal Ontology] based Palaeography thus requiring a certain degree of granularity, e.g. like the one depicted above as n.4 (Image n.1). For a taxonomy of palaeographic processes, see Papadaki (2024), forthcoming.

⁹ Benetos, Papadaki, et al. (2024: 232-234).

pachmentizer, a binder is some but a few examples of “agents” that generated the results a researcher of a manuscript observes while working with handwritten text. But an “agent” is not only a material entity, it is rather a dependent entity which depends on some material entity (e.g. an organism, like some type of insect affecting papyrus, parchment, or paper). Therefore, the specific insect that caused the hole you observe in this specific area of the object you work with can be considered an individual of a class “insect”, which in turn “is” a sub-class of a class “organism”, and so on, as illustrated in the following image.

Image 4: Nested classes as subclasses in a more advanced taxonomy, providing palaeographers all necessary entities for more complex, “has-type” relationships.

Image 5: A hole¹⁰ in Abrincensis Latinus 236, f. 2r, above lin. 6 [=main area interlineare space n. 5].

An “agent” can therefore consider “something” or “someone” who for a time interval adopts a “role” and generates the result an observer at some time instant or time interval perceives as such. Clearly for a palaeographers’ mind a “role” is not a material entity; it might consider an immaterial one, but in comparison to the clearly immaterial “hole”¹¹, one starts to have second thoughts. Having increased the granulation level, soon a researcher agrees that a “role” is not independent (as e.g. objects), but specially dependent entity, such as the color of a stroke, the shape of the hole e.g. in the Abrincensis (see above), or a large amount of additional terms used in palaeography: glyphs, scripts, letters, signs, marks, geometric shapes, styles, parchment qualities, and so on.

¹⁰ I intentionally avoid the generic term “damage”, the granularity level of which demands more than one interconnected entity.

¹¹ For BFO (Basic Formal Ontology, i.e. the model that lies beyond all relationships depicted in this paper), material and immaterial entities comprise the two subclasses of the independent continuant.

Image 5: Subclasses of the [BFO] specifically dependent continuant, that serves for the mother-class of many subclasses containing other nested classes, and so on. On the right of the image, individuals of the class “person role” illustrate the specific “person role” a person/human can adopt while working with handwritten text. When this granularity level has been achieved, the list is considered expandable, and more individuals can be added.

Till now we just increased the taxonomic granularity of all entities needed for a better understanding on any “agent” observed in handwritten sources, yet we haven’t directly answered this question, which brings us to the need of acknowledging a third basic taxonomic branch, the instances of which “generically depend” on other entities; these “generically dependent continuant entities” suit to the nature of an “agent”, providing a solid answer to our question: an “agent” can be considered a generically dependent continuant that generically depends on an object (see e.g. the taxonomy of the Image n.4) which in turn is bearer of some role (see e.g. the taxonomy of image n. 5).

Image 6: Agent as a sub-sub-class of the [BFO] generically dependent continuant.

Following this approach, any specific insect can now be considered an “agent” for the specific “hole” you observed, which in turn is an immaterial entity present in e.g. a side of a folium, that “is a continuant part of” a bifolium, and so on. These assertions comprise interconnections of individuals used in Palaeography, illustrated in the case of “agent” as follows; they are object properties, that is assertions of “has-type” interconnecting entities taxonomically belonging to some branch (class), as shown before. While an agent might generically depend on an organism, it might also depend on a process like “oxidation”, which is clearly not dependent on some organism, but e.g. to arosion caused by water and so on. Therefore an “agent” generically depends on an organism OR is concretized by a

process (e.g. “oxidation”). For codicologists and palaeographers such well-defined approaches can trigger specific inferences during further process, e.g. Critical Editing.

● ('is concretized by at some time' **only process**) or ('generically depends on at some time' **only organism**)

Image 7: Object properties (in black, bold characters between single quote-marks) connecting via “has-type” relationship an “agent” to individuals belonging to the class “organism” OR to the class “process”, followed by a universal restriction (only).

Examples on Classes and Object properties: “Hand” and “Hand shift”

In paleography, the term “hand” empirically refers to the distinct style of writing employed by a scribe, a concept crucial for the study of historical manuscripts, as it allows researchers to identify various hands implying various persons who may have worked on a particular handwritten source. Each “hand” is characterized by features referring to shape, glyph type, spacing, delimiters and ligatures, as well as other entities reflecting either a regional or period-specific conventions, or even the idiographic style of the scribe. A “hand” can reveal much about descriptive processes that occur while decoding a handwritten source, generating utilizable information for further processes such as critical editing.¹²

For an ontology-based Palaeography, “hand” neither is perceived as a fiat object part, nor as an object, therefore the term is unsuitable for material entity dependency. A palaeographic hand is clearly *not* a style, thus not a quality, and the term seems rather semantically closer to the aforementioned “agent”, might it be a subclass or a sibling one of it. A “suspicious” palaeographic hand frequently appears in specific topological area, but no one can firmly argue that topology generically triggers solid evidence about “hand-shift”. Here are two extracts to illustrate the argumentation that follows.

Image 8: Einsiedlensis Latinus p. 153, lin. 19 [interlinear space n.18 included].

¹² In addition to providing insights into the development of writing techniques and the influence of various scripts on each other, hands also offer information about the approximate date and place of origin of handwritten objects. They provide a deeper understanding of a scribe's training and the manuscript production process; while codicologists and palaeographers recognize various hands, they contribute to the reconstruction of practices applied in scriptoria, but such information goes beyond the scope of the present paper.

Image 9: Einsiedlensis Latinus p. 153, lin. 21 [plus main area interlinear space n. 20].

For an observer, the “hand” apparent in the main area text row (which comprises a “site”, arising from the strokes created by the scribe) is clearly identical between these two extracts. With quite a high certainty degree one could acknowledge this very same “hand” as the responsible for the strokes perceived as *bi* (image n.9), which offers a variant reading for the in-row *augetur: augebitur*. For the granularity the online image provides this does not seem the case of the image n.8: the hand appearing in the interlinear-space could quite accurately considered different from the one of the in-row text, and the certainty degree strongly depends on semantics: for syntactical, thus semantic, reasons the phrase *ut in numeris* (“as it happens in numbers”) written *alia manu* and located *supra lineam* resembles a commentary, an observation implying some temporal distance from the time interval needed for the natural hand of the person denoted by the paleographic “hand” of the in-row text to write the relevant text. Might be a tool¹³ or a person shift or both, a “palaeographic” hand is not the physical hand of a person, and rather refers to a generically dependent continuant which depends on both a person and a tool. This approach follows the argumentation developed while describing the nature of a palaeographic “agent”; in the following image “manus” has been classified as a sibling class of “agent”, nevertheless one might suggest that it could be a subclass of it. Alternatives are quite tricky while modeling a large number of information depending on the observer’s perception.

Image 10: Palaeographic “hand” (manus) as a sibling class of “agent” (generically dependent continuant). Such a perspective enhances the ability of palaeographers to identify individual scribes arising from “hand shifts”, an inference deriving in critical apparatuses¹⁴ from the Latin

¹³ Agati (2017: 264-271).

¹⁴ For the additional information apparent in critical apparatuses see e.g. Brown (1993: 24).

note *alia manu(s)*¹⁵. While the natural “hand” of a scribe and the palaeographic “hand” are not identical and can lead to misunderstandings in utterances “another hand wrote this text-row”, “hand-shift” do not need further explanatory statements; under the condition that “hand-shift” is quite meaningful when referring to the same topological area where a previous palaeographic “hand” – serving as one of the two compared “hands” – is located in. Thus, it is rather meaningless in Palaeography to refer to “hand-shift” while comparing a “hand” of an inline-row text with the “hand” observed in anchored-strokes¹⁶ located above or the anchor-ones, as illustrated in the image n.8. Finally, the distinction between a natural “hand” and a palaeographic one can at some point facilitated by the Latin name *manus*, to avoid misunderstanding.

Well-defined entities and the *pers se* Transcription

All the aforementioned comprise what we perceive as the fundamental components for larger theoretical inferences that can be applied to a crucial process which is considered to be a subclass of the BFO occurrent: transcription. Transcription “is” therefore an occurrent and “has occurrent parts” other occurrents as well as some “participants”¹⁷. In a traditional level transcriptional technique remains in quite an empirical¹⁸ frame, but for the well-defined entities ontology-based Palaeography supports, transcription comprises a process that also needs well-defining.

One might consider anything displayed on a computer screen an array composed of Unicode characters that has qualities¹⁹ attributed to these specific Unicode character by their typist; these Unicode characters nothing more than **pinpoints** – this is a crucial word: transcription is now considered the construction of a topological graph comprised by all topologically connected pinpoints, meaningful for the reader thanks to additional properties these pinpoints accumulate according to the transcribers observation.²⁰

¹⁵ See e.g. Maniaci (1996: 161); Parkes (2016: 10, 307); Clemens, Graham (2007:83).

¹⁶ Which comprise what we perceive as marginal, interlinear or intercolumnar text. For margins emerged while creating manuscript structure from a regularized, mostly square or rectangle invisible frame that contains text, see Maniaci (1996: 154-155); Muzerelle (1985: 342); Gumbert (2010 draft: 54-61).

¹⁷ The fundamental BFO object properties governing occurrents are “has occurrent part” and “has participant”, for occurrences and independent entities participating in an occurrent.

¹⁸ Guarino (2009: 4-7).

¹⁹ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 96-97).

²⁰ This definition of transcription provides solid arguments to separate annotation from transcription; while transcription can be achieved e.g. by machine – at least at some point – via already applied techniques worldwide, the properties of an array fall into annotation. Here is a typical example on the Abrincensis Latinus 236. f. 34v, lin. 10-13, illustrating the difference between these two distinct occurrents.

Conclusions

We can now come to some conclusions arising from the theoretical problems we dealt with.

- Ontology based Palaeography arises from the need to create solid relational models for a significant number of entities handwritten sources contain, which are till nowadays perceived by an observer quite empirically because of the lack of a system that supports palaeographic assertions and inferences generated by.
- While transcription is applied in all historical periods, it's study and modern practice can be achieved if and only if it is supported by ontology-based, that is well-defined, palaeographic entities; this mean that transcription has to be treated as a *per se* occurrent in a paleographic model generating solid inferences. In turn this infers that for property assignments (annotation) to the pinpoints transcription generates, any reader of a handwritten source is needed, for semantic reasons that exceed simple topological recognition.
- Finally, Ontology-based Palaeography is a modern field that demands specialists, especially Philologists, Palaeographers and Codicologists to upgrade their armory while working with text, adopting and at the same time developing tools that support thorough analysis and produce results based on structured, deeply annotated data.

It is evident that topology itself generates rather meaningless arrays if one does clearly separate transcription from annotation, which is not tied to the topological structure of a manuscript: it lies on semantics and seeks for solutions on misunderstandings that might happen. Nevertheless, transcription and annotation these rather occur simultaneously while transcribing, and is quite impossible to separate them without a digit platform supporting well-defined palaeographic entities. Finally, we have to admit that even scribes were empirically familiar with the concept of annotation: the scribe shifts from topology to annotation via a rubrica, see e.g. Maniaci (1996: 168, 171).

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